

biomass production at 60 DAS was determined, with GDD calculated as

$$GDD = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{(T_{\max} + T_{\min})}{2} - T_{\text{base}} \right]$$

where T_{\max} , T_{\min} , and T_{base} (10°C) are the maximum, minimum, and base temperature, respectively.

Biomass production and seed production were significantly influenced by the month of sowing. Velvet bean performed better in all the months compared with sunn hemp and Pillipesara. Both velvet bean and sunn hemp produced maximum biomass when planted in June (see table). The shorter growth period and low temperature restricted vegetative growth, and thus biomass production was the lowest in the winter months. All crops flowered earlier when sown in September. Velvet bean took only 50 d to reach 50% flowering when sowed in October-November, but the crop took 32-34 d longer when sowed in May-July (see table).

All crops produced the most seed when sowed in February because of more solar radiation and greater photosynthetic activity during this period. The crops performed better in kharif (monsoon) than in rabi (winter). The correlation between GDD and biomass production was highly significant in velvet bean at 60 DAS (see figure). AGDD greater than 1000 is more favorable for biomass production. When GDD is less than 900, biomass production decreased. ■

Effect of sowing time on biomass production, days to 50% flowering, and seed yield. Coimbatore, India. 1993-94.

Month of sowing	Biomass (t ha^{-1}) 60 DAS			Days to 50% flowering			Seed yield (kg ha^{-1})		
	Pillipesara	Sunn hemp	Velvet bean	Pillipesara	Sunn hemp	Velvet bean	Pillipesara	Sunn hemp	Velvet bean
Oct 1993	4.9	6.2	12.3	45.0	48.6	50.3	346	403	1421
Nov 1993	4.4	6.9	12.0	46.7	48.3	50.7	291	388	1306
Dec 1993	4.9	5.2	11.0	46.0	47.6	63.3	310	462	1317
Jan 1994	5.8	6.5	12.8	44.3	48.7	61.7	376	565	1406
Feb 1994	6.0	8.0	15.1	44.3	49.7	80.3	381	713	1560
Mar 1994	5.0	8.0	14.6	45.7	47.3	81.7	352	611	1549
Apr 1994	4.7	9.0	14.1	45.0	49.3	80.7	349	410	1530
May 1994	5.0	9.3	13.4	48.0	49.0	82.0	312	367	1517
Jun 1994	4.3	9.8	15.6	47.0	45.7	84.3	343	662	1510
Jul 1994	4.6	7.5	15.0	47.0	47.3	63.6	311	546	1457
Aug 1994	3.5	7.0	13.3	46.0	49.3	63.6	311	546	1457
Sep 1994	3.9	5.8	12.1	36.3	36.0	59.3	285	361	1294
SE	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.6	6.0	17.7	7.4
CD	0.3	0.2	0.8	1.5	1.6	1.2	12.6	36.7	15.4

Biomass production (t ha^{-1})

Correlation between growing degree days and biomass production in velvet bean at 60 DAS.

Vermicompost: a potential supplement to nitrogenous fertilizer in rice nutrition

R. Rani and O. P. Srivastava, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University Varanasi 221005, Uttar Pradesh, India

Integrated use of chemical and organic fertilizer is important to sustain a higher level of soil fertility and productivity. Some species of earthworms—

Peironyx excavatus, *Perionyx sansibarius*, *Drazwida willsi*, and *Dichopster bolau* are efficient users of organic wastes. They convert these wastes into good-quality manure in 45 d rather than 4-5 mo with ordinary composting. Nutrient content of ordinary compost ranges from 0.5 to 1.0% N, 0.17 to 0.34% P, and 0.66 to 1.2% K. Vermicompost (VC) used in this experiment contained 1.347% N, 1.12% P, and 1.06% K.

A pot experiment was conducted using a randomized complete block

design with four replications to study the effect of different combinations of VC and urea fertilizer on yield and N utilization of rice (Saket 4). Experimental soil has pH 7.8, EC 0.165 dS m^{-1} , CEC 11.25 $\text{meq } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ soil, organic carbon 0.56%, and available amounts of 260 kg N ha^{-1} , 9.17 kg P ha^{-1} , and 130 kg K ha^{-1} .

Earthen pots were filled with 9 kg soil and 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted. Nitrogen, P_2O_5 , and K_2O were applied at the rate of 60, 30, and 30

ppm. Abasal dose of one-third N and a full dose of P and K were applied at the time of transplanting and the remaining two-thirds applied in two split doses after 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DAT).

A significant increase in number of effective panicles (at 55 DAT), plant height (at 55 DAT), and grain yield (g pot⁻¹) was observed with the integrated treatment combination (T2) vs the full dose of fertilizer alone (T1). Treatment T2 (two-thirds N through fertilizer + one-third N through VC) was on a par with T3 (three-fourths N through fertilizer + one-fourth N through VC) (Table 1). A significant increase in N uptake was also found with treatment T2.

When inorganic fertilizer was added in soil along with organic manure, the availability of N in the form of ammoniacal N continued to be higher for a longer period (Table 2), showing better compatibility and efficiency of combined organic and inorganic sources. Agronomic efficiency in terms of increase in grain yield (g) per gram of

Table 1. Effect of different combinations of VC and fertilizer N on rice. Uttar Pradesh, India. 1994 wet season.

Treatment	Effective panicles (no.) (55 DAT)	Plant height (cm) (55 DAT)	Grain yield (g pot ⁻¹)	Straw yield (g pot ⁻¹)	N in straw (%)	N in grain (%)	N uptake (g pot ⁻¹)
T0 Control	7.4	51.0	6.5	9.8	0.42	0.85	0.10
T1 Full dose N through fertilizer	20.0	57.6	16.1	24.7	0.61	1.12	0.34
T2 2/3 N (fertilizer) + 1/3 N (VC)	24.6	62.4	18.6	26.2	0.65	1.19	0.38
T3 3/4 N (fertilizer) + 1/4 N (VC)	23.1	61.3	17.8	27.6	0.63	1.16	0.38
LSD (0.05)	3.1	3.8	1.8	2.4	0.07	0.09	0.04

added N was 18 for fertilizer N and 21 for fertilizer N + VC, whereas the values of physiological efficiency in terms of increase in grain yield (g) per gram of increase in N uptake were 40 for fertilizer N and 44 for fertilizer N + VC.

Combined application of inorganic fertilizer (two-thirds N) and VC (one-third N) is promising for better fertilizer management. Before making recommendations, the performance of these combinations must be evaluated in farmers' fields. ■

Table 2. Release pattern of NH₄⁺-N under waterlogged conditions.

Treatment	NH ₄ ⁺ -N (ppm)		
	7 d	14 d	21 d
Control	38.74	43.05	45.74
100 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	118.75	123.10	125.73
100 ppm N through VC	72.65	106.48	119.07
75 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 25 ppm N through VC	124.62	130.49	135.61
50 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 50 ppm N through VC	122.75	129.01	136.61
25 ppm N through (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 75 ppm N through VC	96.62	118.61	128.02

Integrated pest management—diseases

Two Myanma isolates of rice tungro bacilliform virus belong to the Southeast Asian strain

A. Druka, John Innes Centre (JIC), Virus Research Department, Colney, Norwich NR4 7UH, United Kingdom; Thane Htay and Aung Baw, Plant Protection Division, Myanmar Agricultural Service, Bayintnaung Road, West Jyogone, Insein, Yangon, Myanmar; and Roger Hull, JIC

Rice tungro is one of the most devastating rice diseases in South and Southeast Asia. It is caused by two viruses, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). RTBV is responsible for symptom development. Its transmission by leafhopper depends on RTSV which, by itself, does not cause marked symptoms.

Two strains of RTBV have been reported previously, one from the Indian subcontinent, the other from Southeast Asia. The nearest that two RTBV strains were found is Assam in India, Dhaka in Bangladesh (Indian strain), and central Thailand, a distance of about 1500 km. These two regions are not separated by a rice-free area; Myanmar produces considerable rice. Although tungro has been suspected to occur in Myanmar, it has not been identified there. We were interested in seeing which RTBV strain can be found in Myanmar.

Samples with tungro symptoms were collected from the fields around Yangon (Baular, Hlegu, Central Rice Model Farm, Tookyng) and around Mandalay (Pathenlay, Amarapura, and

Kankank). The quick assay for differentiation of strains is by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), around a 64-bp deletion, which is characteristic for the Indian strain. Degenerate primer sequences used for PCR are as follows: direct 5'-GAASAAGTACCATGACCATGAATACN (position 7743-7763 in RTBV genome) and reverse 5'-CACCCCGGGKRWNGCTCTGATACCA (position 17-1 in RTBV genome). The ambiguities are K = G or T, M = A or C, R = A or G, S = C or G, and W = A or T. PCR results have shown that samples collected near Mandalay (Amarapura) and Yangon (Baular) are infected with RTBV; we were not able to detect RTBV in other samples. The size of the PCR products is 280 bp, which indicates no